

PREPARATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY THROUGH DIGITALIZATION AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract: The article deals with the peculiarities of introducing modern educational resources into the process of preparing future teachers for pedagogical activity by means of digitization, and describes a general analysis of theoretical-based approaches to the possibility of introducing tasks for the design, development, use and experimental evaluation of modern educational resources.

Keywords: pedagogy, educational-methodological training, educational resources, professional training of future teachers, digitization of education.

Today, in our republic, important and meritorious works are being carried out in order to modernize the education system, introduce innovative teaching technologies, train young people with professional qualities such as independence, creativity, initiative, entrepreneurship, and encourage pedagogues. The use of pedagogical innovations in the educational process is a global trend of world development, which, in turn, requires special attention to the systematic introduction of innovations into the field of education due to the rapid development of the modernization process in the country. The "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, developed on the basis of the presidential decree, calls for the complete elimination of digital illiteracy, the formation of a technological base and the establishment of skills training in the coming years.

Over the past 15 years, the scientific community has been actively discussing the positive and negative aspects of digitization of education. Some researchers approve of such a change in the educational system, while others are against it, rejecting any information about the positive features of the introduction of digital media into the educational process.

Theoretical and practical aspects of the search and creation of new digital teaching tools have been considered several times in scientific and pedagogical circles. Thus, in particular, N.V. Gafurova, V.V. Grinshkun, M.P. Lapchik, S.V. Panyukova, N.I. Pak, I.V. Robert, O.G. Smolyaninova, A.Yu. Uvarov, I.S. The works of authors such as Frumin [6] make it possible to determine the methodological foundations necessary for the design, development and competent use of digital educational tools today. In addition, due to the need to implement the

requirements of state educational standards of general education, the development of new educational resources for teaching students of the modern generation from the point of view of the questioning approach is described in more detail. [4].

In our republic, in recent years, the normative foundations of the formation of mechanisms for the gradual transfer of higher education organizations to a credit-modular system, improvement of state educational standards taking into account the modern requirements of the economy, development of a base for the effective organization of educational and production practices of students are being created. "Increasing the share of independent education hours, students' independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, practical control of the educational process "directing to the formation of skills, in this regard, the wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and teaching-methodical materials to the educational process based on international educational standards" was set as a priority. This expands the pedagogical possibilities of development models of future engineers, development by means of information technologies.

The use of digital technologies in education in additional fields is already being implemented by many higher educational institutions in America, Europe and Russia, digital libraries and digital university departments are being developed.

Another important aspect of digital technology in education is its ability to enhance collaboration and communication. With online platforms like Google Classroom, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom, students can collaborate on projects, share documents, and communicate with each other and their teachers regardless of their physical location. This allows students to work effectively in collaboration, exchange ideas and learn from each other.

In addition, digital education technology has made it possible for students to study from anywhere in the world. Online education has opened up opportunities for students who may not have access to traditional educational resources, such as those in remote or underserved areas. Online courses and programs also allow students to study at their own pace and schedule, making education more convenient for those with other commitments such as work or family.

Digital technologies - augmented reality, the most promising - augmented reality technology that allows adding objects from the virtual world to the real world. Imagine walking down the street and seeing more information about things and people around you. Examples of augmented reality already exist and are actively used, in some amusement parks you can already see signs that show the connections between objects in the physical world and the virtual world. Games with elements of augmented reality are actively spreading, clothing stores have virtual windows and fitting rooms, augmented reality is already being tested in cars. At the same time, there are issues that need to be resolved in order to actively use augmented reality technologies. For example, the accuracy of geolocation tools is still insufficient, or the computer vision technologies for connecting objects of the physical world with their virtual counterparts are imperfect. However, it is safe to say that in the near future this technology may be associated with breakthroughs.

Despite the many benefits of digital technology in education, there are also some challenges that need to be addressed. The digital divide is one of the biggest challenges. Not all students have the necessary digital devices or reliable internet connections, which can lead to disparities in learning opportunities. It is therefore essential to ensure that all students have access to the necessary digital technology to fully participate in digital learning.

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